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Consumer Behavior towards Cafes in General Luna, Quezon

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Abstract

This study aims to explore consumer behavior towards cafes in General Luna, Quezon, focusing on understanding consumer profiles and the factors influencing cafe visitation. The consumer profile will cover age, civil status, sex, occupation, and address, serving as bases for segmenting customer groups. Using a descriptive research design, the study will describe the respondents' demographic characteristics, beliefs about visiting cafes, sources of influence, and actual behavior towards cafes. Additionally, descriptive correlation will identify relationships between these variables. Respondents will consist of cafe consumers in General Luna, Quezon. They will be identified through two methods: referrals from cafe owners and on-site observation from July 2024 onwards. Due to the challenge of identifying all potential respondents, the researcher will apply a snowball sampling technique, where initial respondents will refer others. The researcher will design a survey questionnaire grounded in consumer behavior theories, including the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Theory of Reasoned Action. The questionnaire will undergo validation by a panel to ensure reliability. Data will be analyzed using Frequency and Percentage Distribution, Mean, Standard Deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The study will assess consumers' attitudes toward cafe visits, sources of influence, and the degree of behavioral control, including self-efficacy and facilitating conditions. It will also examine the relationship between consumer profiles and their attitudes, influences, behavioral control, and intention or actual behavior towards cafe visits. Ultimately, the study seeks to determine how attitudes, influence, and control predict consumers' intention and actual visits to cafes in General Luna, Quezon.

Keywords: *behavior, consumer, cafes*

Introduction

This study focused on understanding consumer behavior toward cafés in General Luna, Quezon. Cafés, typically small restaurants, primarily serve coffee, tea, and light refreshments like baked goods or snacks. The word "café" originates from the French term for "coffee." In General Luna, there are five notable cafés: Kape Luna, Food Corner, Belrico Café and Resto, King Boba, and Anna's Restaurant. The study explored the extent to which consumers frequent these cafés, examining their patterns and preferences when visiting cafés in the area.

The primary objective of the research was to identify the motivations behind consumers' visits to cafés. It investigated how individuals allocate their resources—time, money, and effort—when choosing to visit a café. Specifically, the study analyzed factors such as the reasons for visiting, the timing and frequency of visits, and purchasing behaviors. Additionally, the research considered how beliefs, attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence consumer intentions. These factors can shape motivations and, in turn, lead to changes in behavior, which may vary depending on the specific context of the visit, including its purpose, timing, and frequency.

Consumer behavior seems to be an eminent study to understand the model into the extents of the consumers' desire to visit a café in General Luna, Quezon. Recently, the process of human visitation, which has been presented from the beginning, was initially an activity that must be fulfilled for the rest of life, whereas today it has been the goal of life. Today, visitation is no longer a process due to the needs of consumers but, in accordance with their wishes, has become an evolving process. The concepts of "customer focus" and "customer loyalty" in modern marketing require audience recognition. Consumer behavior has focused attention and studies on what was perceived as the presence of a very strong and powerful force in nations' economies. In fact, the world is a world of consumers. It is the consumers who make the industry go around. It is the consumer who ultimately decides what must be produced or not produced and, as a consequence, the level of standard of living that people want and enjoy.

Normative beliefs are one of the reasons why people encourage visiting a cafe. This has influenced consumer behavior in order to intentionally push another person to change their attitudes. Influence on others is characterized by an individual behaving in a certain way to gain power over another person. This study of the relationship between intention, beliefs, and attitude held by a person offers one possible route towards a better understanding of the influence of different factors on consumer behavior. The consumer seldom knows what he or she wants.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents' in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. civil status;

- 1.3. gender;
- 1.4. job/occupation;
- 1.5. educational attainment; and
- 1.6. address?
2. What is the attitude of the respondents' in terms of their:
 - 2.1. beliefs in the visitation of cafes; and
 - 2.2. affective state generated by the visitation of a cafe?
3. Who influences the respondents' decision to visit a cafe, and to what extent do they comply with such influence?
4. To what extent do the respondents actually visit cafes or intend to visit cafe?
5. To what extent do the respondents have behavioral control when visiting cafes in terms of:
 - 5.1. self-efficacy in visiting a café; and
 - 5.2. Facilitating conditions in the visitation of cafes?
6. To what extent does the respondents profile significantly relate to their:
 - 6.1. attitudes toward visiting cafes;
 - 6.2. influence of significant others to visit cafes;
 - 6.3. perceived behavioral control in visiting cafes; and
 - 6.4. intention or actual behavior of visiting cafes?
7. To what extent is the intention to visit cafes or the actual behavior of visiting cafes significantly related to:
 - 7.1. Attitude;
 - 7.2. influence of significant others; and
 - 7.3. perceived behavioral control?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive method will be used to describe the respondents in terms of their demographic profile, their beliefs with regard to the visitation of cafes, the sources of influence in terms of cafe visitation, and their behavior towards cafes. Descriptive correlation will be used to determine the extent and direction of the relationship among the variables.

Respondents

The respondents of this study are the consumers of cafes, which are located in General Luna, Quezon. To identify the respondents, two strategies will be employed: 1.) asking the cafe owners for consumers they know within the Municipality of General Luna, Quezon, and neighboring towns and over; and 2.) Spotting buyers on site from July 2024 to present. Since it is assumed that not all in the prospective population may visit, all identified consumers or buyers will be deemed potential respondents.

The researcher will use a non-probabilistic sampling technique called the snowball technique in order to identify prospective respondents to the study.

Prospective respondents must have experienced visiting cafes in General Luna, Quezon, for at least one instance prior to the conduct of this study or have an intention to visit them.

Instrument

To come up with strong and valid data, the researcher crafted a research instrument from the theories of consumer behavior, the Theory of Planned Behavior, and the Theory of Reasoned Action. The survey questionnaire is crafted for the purpose of the study and will be validated by the panelists. The design aims to gather and establish evidence of consumer behavior in cafes in General Luna, Quezon.

The first part covers the demographic profile of the respondents to identify their age, sex, job or occupation, and address. The second part dealt with the consumer's attitude, the influence of significant others, perceived behavioral control, consumer intention, and actual visitation of cafes with 44 questions utilizing the 6-likert scale: Very Strongly Agree, Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree and Very Strongly Disagree.

The researcher assumes that the instrument has context validity since the items were formulated based on the Theory of Planned Behavior. The reliability of the instrument will be established using Cronbach's alpha.

Data Analysis

To extract meaningful information from the data, the following statistical treatment will be used:

Frequency Count and Percentage: summarize the data on civil status, gender, job or occupation, educational attainment, and place of origin.

Mean and Standard Deviation: to provide a summary of the age and household size of the respondents and to describe the respondent's

beliefs and affective states generated by the visitation of cafes as well as their behavior related to the visitation of cafes.

Pearson Product Correlation Coefficient: to determine the extent and direction of the relationship of the respondents' profile to age, civil status, gender, job or occupation, educational attainment, and place of origin to attitudes towards visiting, influence of significant others to visit cafes, perceived behavioral control on visiting cafes, and intention or actual behavioral of visiting cafes.

Results and Discussion

This chapter with presentation, analysis and interpretation of data. It analyzed data based on different statistical treatment and interprets data according to the topic, Consumer Behavior towards Cafes in General Luna, Quezon.

Sub-problem 1. What is the profile of the respondents' in terms of age, civil status, gender, job/occupation, educational attainment, address?

The table 1 shows the profile of respondents of 202 respondents according to their age, civil status, gender, job/occupation, and educational attainment. The typical respondents of this study is 21 years old, female and a college students. She is a Teacher, Municipal employee, students, Business owner and housewives.

Table 1. Demographic profile of the respondents

Variables	f	%	Mean	St.Dev.
Age	200	100	21	13.17
Civil Status	200	100		
Married	78	38.44		
Single	114	56.44		
Widow	8	3.96		
Separated	2	0.99		
Gender	200	100		
Male	91	45.05		
Female	111	54.95		
Educational Attainment	200	100		
Graduate degree	19	9.41		
College students	112	55.45		
High School Graduates	12	5.94		
High School students	47	23.27		
Elementary Graduates	9	4.46		
Elementary students	3	1.49		
Job/Occupation	200	100		
Municipal Employee	18	8.91		
Farmers	6	2.97		
Business Owner	20	9.9		
Professional	28	13.86		
Machine operator and semi-skilled Workers	18	8.91		
Housewives	21	10.4		
Unskilled workers	3	1.49		
Students	69	34.16		
None	19	9.41		

Sub-problem 2. What is the attitude of the respondents' in terms of their beliefs in the visitation of cafes and Evaluating the Consequences of visiting Cafes?

Table 2. Attitudes of consumers towards Cafe

Dimension	f	Mean	St.Dev.
Affective state			
A1 Good vs. Bad	200	5.35	1.08
A2 Pleasant vs Unpleasant	200	5.31	1.02
A3 Desirable vs. Undesirable	200	5.35	0.99
A4 Relaxing vs. Stressful	200	4.9	1.49
Personal Relative Advantage			
PRA Enjoyment	200	30.03	11.52
Societal Relative Advantage			
SRA Actual Identity	200	24.09	12.34

Key: (A1, A2, A3, A4 & A5) (PRA, SRA)
 1.00-1.83 Extremely bad, unpleasant, undesirable, stressful 1.00-6.84 Very strongly disagree, not important at all
 1.84-2.66 Very bad, unpleasant, undesirable, stress 8.85-13.69 Strongly disagree, not so important
 2.67-3.49 Bad, unpleasant, undesirable, stressful 13.70-25.39 Disagree, not important
 3.50-4.32 Good, pleasant, desirable, relaxing 25.40-34.24 Agree, important
 4.33-5.16 Very good, pleasant, desirable, relaxing 34.25-41.09 Strongly agree, very important
 5.17-6.00 Extremely good, pleasant, desirable, relaxing 41.10-49.00 Very strongly agree, extremely important

Table 2 shown that consumers find visiting café as very good ($x = 5.35$, St. dev. = 1.08), very pleasant ($x = 5.31$, St. dev. = 1.02), very desirable ($x = 5.35$, St. dev. = 0.99) and relaxing ($x = 4.90$, St. dev. = 1.49). Consumers indicate greatest homogeneity in responses that visiting cafes is very desirable (St. dev. = 0.99). They indicate greatest heterogeneity in responses that visiting cafes is relaxing (St. dev. = 1.49).

Consumers satisfaction in visiting café depend upon to their experienced of visiting cafes. How they become satisfied on visitation may classified on their favorable feelings as good, pleasant, desirable or relaxing and on their unfavorable feelings as bad, unpleasant undesirable or stressful.

According to Fishbein and Ajzen in Asiegbu et al 2021, attitude is a learned predisposition to respond or react in a consistently favorable (like) or unfavorable (dislike) manner with respect to a given object/situation. In a simpler definition, Pickens defines attitudes as a mind-set or a tendency to act in a particular way due to both an individuals experience and temperament and the reactions/responds include the tricomponent of feeling (emotions), thoughts (beliefs) and actions (behaviors). It is consistent in Wilson, who studied that the attitudes-behavior relationship were not uni-dimensional as previously thought, but multi-dimensional.

The table 2 illustrated that respondent find a personal relative advantage that enjoyment in visiting café is important ($x = 30.03$, St. dev. = 11.52). The consumers indicate the greatest heterogeneity is enjoyment (St. dev. 11.52).

Enjoyment of visiting café could be important because it is determinant to feel the good café and to understand the enjoyment of consumer is important to decide whether it is good or not for them to visit café.

The consumer find in societal relative advantage that actual identity in visiting café is important ($x = 24.09$, St. dev. = 12.34). The consumers indicate the greatest heterogeneity is actual identity (St. dev. = 12.34).

Sub-problem 3. Who influences the respondents' decision to visit a cafe, and to what extent do they comply with such influence?

Table 3. Subjective norm in the visitation of cafe

Dimension	f	Mean	St.Dev.
Influence of significant others			
SO1 Influential people	200	5.59	1.23
SO2 Important people	200	5.44	2.17
Internal Normative Beliefs			
INB1 Family	200	25.90	12.07
INB2 Friends	200	26.85	12.14
External Normative Beliefs			
ENB1 Colleagues	200	27.19	9.77
ENB2 Social Media	200	25.95	12.97

Key: (A1, A2, A3, A4 & A5) (PRA, SRA)

1.00-1.83 Extremely bad, unpleasant, undesirable, stressful	1.00-6.84 Very strongly disagree, not important at all
1.84-2.66 Very bad, unpleasant, undesirable, stress	8.85-13.69 Strongly disagree, not so important
2.67-3.49 Bad, unpleasant, undesirable, stressful	13.70-25.39 Disagree, not important
3.50-4.32 Good, pleasant, desirable, relaxing	25.40-34.24 Agree, important
4.33-5.16 Very good, pleasant, desirable, relaxing	34.25-41.09 Strongly agree, very important
5.17-6.00 Extremely good, pleasant, desirable, relaxing	41.10-49.00 Very strongly agree, extremely important

Table 3 illustrated the respondents' subjective norms in visitation of café. The consumer find in subjective norm that influence of significant others like influential people in eating visiting cafes is strongly agree ($x = 5.59$, St. dev. = 1.23) and the important people in visiting cafe is strongly agree ($x = 5.44$, St. dev. = 1.17). Consumers indicate the greatest homogeneity that influence in visiting is the influential people (St. dev. = 1.23) and they indicate that the greatest heterogeneity in responses that visiting cafe is from important people (St. dev. = 1.17).

It means that the effect of influential people and important people is strongly agree to encourage in visiting cafe. However, consumer decision making within the influential and important people has begun to receive a growing amount of attention with increased realization of the effect that each individual within the consumer activities of this primary social groups.

According to Kotler & Armstrong 2021, through doing and learning, people acquire beliefs and attitudes. These, in turn, influence their buying behavior. A belief is a descriptive thought that a person has about something. The beliefs may be based on real knowledge, opinion, or faith, and may or may not carry an emotional charge.

The respondents find internal normative beliefs in visiting cafe of family is neutral ($x = 25.90$, St. dev. = 12.07) and friends is good ($x = 26.85$, St. dev. = 12.14). The consumers indicate the greatest homogeneity in visiting café is family (St. dev. = 12.07). They also indicate that the most heterogeneity in visiting cafe is friends (St. dev. = 12.14).

The aforementioned pointed out that the consumers agree that their family and friends influenced them for visiting cafe. It has taken some time for consumer decision making to acknowledge the family and friends as a central visiting group. Lot of people would say that friends have more influence than family on behavioral consumption. Some believe that family is the most important. Different people have different angles of thoughts, Consumers influenced by their family a lot, since they know them their whole life and friends may have more influence but sometimes it depends on family and society on how they influenced. In contrast, it still depends on

consumers' personality if they want to be influenced more by friends or family.

According to Haller and Woelfel the influence of significant others is the most concept available for use in assessing interpersonal influence on orientational variables.

The respondents find external normative beliefs in significant of colleagues is agree ($x = 27.19$, St. dev. = 9.77) and the social media is agree ($x = 25.95$, St. dev. = 12.97). Consumers indicate the greatest homogeneity in responses of the subjective norm in visitation in café is social media (St. dev. = 12.97). They indicate greatest heterogeneity in responses of the subjective norm in visitation cafe is the colleagues (St. dev. = 9.77).

Based on Lutz, behavior toward media commercials of obtaining goods is an essential concept, as it is one of the determining factors of people's behavior. According to Rogers and Singhai, the social media often create awareness- knowledge of an innovation, but the role of interpersonal communication with peers is necessary to persuade most individuals to adopt a new idea within an object or something.

Sub-problem 4. To what extent do the respondents have behavioral control when visiting cafes in terms of self-efficacy in visiting a café and facilitating conditions in the visitation of cafes?

Table 4. *Perceived behavioral control in visiting café*

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>St.Dev.</i>
Sel-decision			
PBC1 Decision in visiting café	200	5.28	1.36
PBC2 Control in visiting café	200	5.28	1.33
PBC3 Stopping in visiting café	200	4.32	1.61
Sel-efficacy			
SE1 Right Choice	200	25.42	13.20
SE2 Right Action	200	32.81	11.58
Facilitating Condition			
F1 Access to my town in terms of decision	200	25.61	14.48
F2 Access to my town in terms of high quality-quality	200	31.35	11.57

Key: (PBC1, PBC2, & PBC3) (SE1, SE2 and FC1, FC2)

1.00-1.83 Very Strongly disagree	1.00-6.84 Very strongly disagree, not important at all
1.84-2.66 Strongly disagree	8.85-13.69 Strongly disagree, not so important
2.67-3.49 Disagree	13.70-25.39 Disagree, not important
3.50-4.32 Agree	25.40-34.24 Agree, important
4.33-5.16 Strongly agree	34.25-41.09 Strongly agree, very important
5.17-6.00 Very strongly agree	41.10-49.00 Very strongly agree, extremely important

Table 4 presented the respondents. Perceived behavioral control in visitation of cafe, Consumers find the self-decision in visiting cafe of their decision is very strongly agree ($x = 5.28$, St. dev. = 1.36), the control is very strongly agree ($x = 5.28$, St. dev. = 1.33) and the stopping is agree ($x = 4.32$, St. dev. = 1.62). Among the three variables of perceived behavioral control in visiting café, responses to the control in visiting café appear to be most homogeneity because it illustrated the lowest standard deviation (St. dev. = 1.33) and the respondents appear to be most heterogeneity in the stopping in visiting café since it has the highest standard deviation (St. dev. = 1.61).

The aforementioned pointed that perceived behavioral control is reflects a person's beliefs as to how easy or difficult it will be to perform the behavior. Consumers' are very strongly agree that it is part on their personal decision on how they will or on what way they will visit café.

According to Ajzen, perceived behavioral control refers to people's perception of their ability to perform a given behavior. It determined by total set of accessible control beliefs people hold that may facilitate or impede performance of the behavior. This reflects the confidence people have that they are capable of performing the target behavior. This was measured by assessing the person's self-efficacy and their facilitating condition about the controllability of consuming a product or service.

The consumers find the self-efficacy in visiting cafe of right choice is agree ($x = 25.42$, St. dev. = 13.20) and the right action is agree ($x = 32.81$, St. dev. = 11.58). Between the two variables of self-efficacy in visiting cafe, responses to the right action appear to be most homogeneity because it illustrates the lowest standard deviation (St.11.58) and the respondents appear to be most heterogeneity in the right choice since it has the highest standard deviation St. dev. = 13.20).

The aforementioned pointed that self-efficacy is the individual perception that he/she will be able to perform a certain behavior. The study resulted as that consumers are agree on their right choice of visiting café and it is important on their right choice visiting café Meanwhile, consumer are agree about their right action on visiting cafe and their right action on visiting is important for them.

Bandura, emphasized that self-efficacy is not a context free global disposition but that, instead it "refers to beliefs in one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to produce given attainments". Clearly, then, one way in which self-efficacy can influence performance of difficult behaviors is by its effect on perseverance. The more people believe that they have the capacity to perform an intended behavior, the more likely they are to persevere and, therefore to succeed.

The consumers find the facilitating condition in visiting cafe access to my town in terms of decision is agree ($x = 25.61$, St. dev. = 14.48) and the access to my town in terms of high quality is important ($x = 31.35$, St. dev. = 11.57). Between the two variables of facilitating condition in visiting cafe, responses to the access to my town in terms of high quality appear to be most homogeneity because it illustrate the lowest standard deviation (St. dev. = 1 1.57) and the respondents appear to be most heterogeneity in the access to my town in terms decision since it has the highest standard deviation (St. dev. = 14.48).

The aforementioned pointed that behavior was considerably affected by individual intention and facilitating condition. It has been found out that consumer agree that visiting cafe from the access to my town in terms of decision is an important part of their decision to visit cafe. Meanwhile, consumers are agree that they have access to my town in terms of high quality café is an important to visit café.

According to Nizen. the measures of actual control are unavailable. Indeed, with respect to many behaviors, it would be let alone measure, the factors that may facilitate or inhibit behavioral performance. It is perhaps for this reason that many investigators rely on measure of perceived behavioral control. This of course assumes that perceptions of behavioral control or veridical, they can serve as a proxy for actual control and contribute to the facilitating condition of consumers. Facilitating condition is the degree to which individual believes that an organizational and technical infrastructure exists to support technology exist.

Sub-problem 5. To what extent do the respondents actually visit cafes or intend to visit cafe?

Table 5. *Intention and actual behavior in visitation of café*

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>St.Dev.</i>
Behavioral Intention			
BI1 Expected Visitation (Socialize)	200	4.71	1.77
BI2 Expected Visitation (Frequency)	200	4.65	1.75
BI3 Expected Visitation (Schedule)	200	4.82	1.39
Actual Visitation			
AV1 Least twice a week	200	25.55	12.49
AV2 Least once every weekend	200	33.93	11.39
Key: (PBC1, PBC2, & PBC3) (SE1, SE2 and FC1, FC2)			
1.00-1.83 Very Strongly disagree		1.00-6.84	Very strongly disagree, not important at all
1.84-2.66 Strongly disagree		8.85-13.69	Strongly disagree, not so important
2.67-3.49 Disagree		13.70-25.39	Disagree, not important
3.50-4.32 Agree		25.40-34.24	Agree, important
4.33-5.16 Strongly agree		34.25-41.09	Strongly agree, very important
5.17-6.00 Very strongly agree		41.10-49.00	Very strongly agree, extremely important

The table 5 presented the respondents intention and actual behavior in visitation of cafe. Consumers find the behavioral intention in visiting café in expected visitation (socialize) is strongly agree ($x = 4.71$, St. dev. = 1.77), in expected visitation (frequency) is strongly agree ($x = 4.65$, St. dev. = 1.75) and in expected visitation (schedule) is strongly agree ($x = 4.82$, St. dev. = 1.39). Among the three variables of behavioral intention in visiting café, responses to the expected visitation (schedule) appear to be the most homogeneity because it posits the lowest standard deviation (St. dev. = 0.39) and the respondents appear to be most heterogeneity in the expected visitation (socialize) since it has the highest standard deviation (St. dev. =1.77).

The aforementioned pointed the consumers' expected visitation (schedule) strongly agree in visiting cafe. However, the consumers' expected visitation (socialize) is strongly agree in visiting café. This behavior indicated the preferred favorable and unfavorable intention of a consumer to when and how they visit café. Based on the literature of Dean Gregory (2017) a consumer can hold negative or positive beliefs or feelings toward a product or service. A behavioral intention is the consumers' belief or feeling with respect to the product or service. Meanwhile, behavioral intention may not yield the expected behavior if the attitudes or other factors of visitation and behavior are not measure at the same level. Intention are expected to lead to performance of the behavior to the extent that people are in fact capable of doing so, i.e., to the extent that they have actual control over the behavior.

The consumer find the actual visitation in visiting cafe of least twice a week is agree ($x = 25.25$, St. dev. 12.49) and least once every weekend is agree ($x = 33.93$, St. 11.39). Among the two variables of actual visitation in visiting cafe, responses in the least once every weekend appear to be most homogeneity because it illustrates the lowest standard deviation (St. dev. 11.39) and the respondents appear to be most heterogeneity in the least twice a week since it has the highest standard deviation (St. dev. = 12.49).

The aforementioned pointed that intention defined plan or goals. people often times fall short of achieving their goals. Behavioral intention is an indication or a person's readiness to perform a given behavior or action. According to Ajzen, actual behavioral control expected to moderate the effect of intention on behavior. However, on the contrary, in many applications of the TPB, it would be difficult or impossible to identify all the factors that influence actual control over performance of the behavior.

Sub-problem 6. To what extent does the respondents profile significantly relate to their attitudes toward visiting cafes, influence of significant others to visit cafes, perceived behavioral control in visiting cafes, and intention or actual behavior of visiting cafes?

The table 6 illustrated the correlation between the demographic profile in terms of age, gender and educational attainment to attitudes toward, influence of significant others, on perceived behavioral control, in intention and visitation of café.

Table 6. *Correlation between the demographic profile and attitudes toward visiting cafes, influence of significant others to visit cafes, perceived behavioral control in visiting cafes, and intention or actual behavior of visiting cafes*

<i>Dimension of visitation cafe</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Educational Attainment</i>
Affective state			
A1 Good vs. Bad	-0.073	0.014	0.082
A2 Pleasant vs Unpleasant	0.004	0.069	0.064
A3 Desirable vs. Undesirable	-0.042	0.010	0.036
A4 Relaxing vs. Stressful	-0.049	0.175	-0.0004
Personal Relative Advantage			
PRA Enjoyment	-0.022	-0.124	-0.125
Societal Relative Advantage			
SRA Actual Identity	-0.032	0.039	-0.024
Influence of significant others			
SO1 Influential people	-0.240	-0.021	-0.117
SO2 Important people	-0.085	-0.018	0.152
Internal Normative Beliefs			
INB1 Family	-0.107	0.077	0.052
INB2 Friends	-0.046	0.078	0.067
External Normative Beliefs			
ENB1 Colleagues	0.125	0.148	-0.037
ENB2 Social Media	0.078	-0.004	0.079
Sel-decision			
PBC1 Decision in visiting café	-0.101	-0.024	0.110
PBC2 Control in visiting café	-0.101	-0.062	0.065
PBC3 Stopping in visiting café	-0.055	-0.099	0.154
Sel-efficacy			
SE1 Right Choice	0.019	0.093	0.095
SE2 Right Action	-0.111	-0.079	0.168
Facilitating Condition			
F1 Access to my town in terms of decision	-0.104	-0.040	0.274
F2 Access to my town in terms of high quality-quality	0.095	-0.042	0.130
Behavioral Intention			
BI1 Expected Visitation (Socialize)	0.002	-0.007	0.053
BI2 Expected Visitation (Frequency)	-0.037	0.040	-0.008
BI3 Expected Visitation (Schedule)	0.027	0.069	-0.060
Actual Visitation			
AV1 Least twice a week	-0.037	0.040	0.096
AV2 Least once every weekend	0.017	0.054	0.056

Critical Value at df=199, sig. 0.05= +/-0.1946

It been said that correlation is significant if the r -value at least +/-0.1946. Based on the statistical measure, the coefficients from the demographic profile in term of age, gender and educational attainment does not show significant relationship between attitudes toward, influence of significant others, on perceived behavioral control, in intention and actual visitation of café. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the demographic profile in terms of age, gender and educational attainment and the dimensions of visiting cafe is totally accepted.

According to Lao and Jacutan, the total consumer group, which is the overall potential market, can be broken down according to the demographic of its population, which includes the consumer age, their gender, jobs and income level, and education level. It may assume that people who belong in a certain age group, experience similar beliefs, values, tastes, and experiences. It could say that a person in the age of 60s and 70s is very different in attitudes, perceptions and purchase behavior than a person in the age of 20s and 30s.

According to Swarna Bakshi, males and females want different products According to Swarna and they are likely to have different ways of liking and obtaining these. Gender has an important role in consumer behaviors because, the differences between men and women are about expectation, want and needs to their visitation behaviors.

Moreover, in influence on behavior, level of schooling is one of the common characteristics by which social scientist categorize people. Yet, for all the examples of strong correlates of education that one might suggest, very little is known about the causes or the nature of these effects. More highly educated people earn different incomes or hold different opinions, but it cannot say whether these differences result from specific knowledge acquired as part of education, from changes in the manner in which decisions are reach, or from changes in basic beliefs and values.

In the study of Marine Pontet and Solene Salaun, consumers profile has an important influence and determinants on the attitude and other factors toward purchasing a product.

However on the contrary, by the study of Ho Soo Fong, age, gender and educational level of the consumer do not effect on consumers' attitude and other factors toward visitation of café.

Sub-Problem 7. To what extent is the intention to visit cafe or the actual behavior of visiting cafes significantly related to attitude, influence of significant others and perceived behavioral control?

The table 7 presented the correlation between the intention to visit cafes or the actual behavior of visiting cafes and attitude, influence of significant others, perceived behavioral control.

Table 7. Correlation between the behavioral intention to visit cafes and the actual behavior of visiting cafes significantly related attitude toward, influence of significant others, on perceived behavioral control?

Dimension of visitation café	Behavioral intention			Actual Visitation	
	B1	B2	B3	AV1	AV2
Affective state					
A1 Good vs. Bad	0.062	0.076	0.079	0.200	0.049
A2 Pleasant vs Unpleasant	0.169	0.121	0.190	0.190	0.070
A3 Desirable vs. Undesirable	0.044	0.126	1.129	0.258	0.120
A4 Relaxing vs. Stressful	-0.004	0.062	0.158	0.190	0.122
Personal Relative Advantage					
PRA Enjoyment	0.058	-0.006	0.036	0.139	0.132
Societal Relative Advantage					
SRA Actual Identity	-0.102	-0.102	0.080	0.122	-0.102
Influence of significant others					
SO1 Influential people	0.030	0.096	-0.044	0.196	0.076
SO2 Important people	0.083	0.058	0.080	0.244	0.192
Internal Normative Beliefs					
INB1 Family	-0.030	0.014	0.143	0.181	0.135
INB2 Friends	-0.040	0.029	0.021	0.152	0.105
External Normative Beliefs					
ENB1 Colleagues	0.026	0.054	0.158	0.141	0.167
ENB2 Social Media	-0.059	-0.129	-0.040	0.112	0.124
Sel-decision					
PBC1 Decision in visiting café	0.049	0.037	0.031	0.151	0.126
PBC2 Control in visiting café	0.086	0.102	-0.024	0.009	0.126
PBC3 Stopping in visiting café	0.031	-0.016	-0.046	0.070	0.062
Sel-efficacy					
SE1 Right Choice	-0.136	-0.137	0.093	0.163	0.087
SE2 Right Action	0.027	0.030	-0.041	0.212	0.049
Facilitating Condition					
F1 Access to my town in terms of decision	-0.038	0.041	-0.059	0.109	0.124
F2 Access to my town in terms of high quality	0.076	0.030	-0.033	0.178	0.185

Critical Value at $df=199, sig. 0.05=+/-0.1946$

It been said that correlation is significant if the r -value is at least $+/-0.1946$. Based on the statistical measure, the coefficients in attitude in terms of the affective state of visiting cafes one as bad or good, three as desirable or undesirable and four as relaxing or stressful is related to the intention to visit on the actual behavior of visiting café but not related to behavioral intention one, two and three-and actual visitation two. The personal relative advantage in terms of enjoyment and societal relative advantage in terms of actual identity does not related to behavioral intention and actual visitation.

The subjective norm in the visitation of café such as influence of significant others in terms of influential people and important people is related to actual visitation one but not related to behavioral intention one, two, three and actual visitation two. On the other hand, internal normative belief in terms of family and friends and external normative beliefs in terms of colleagues and social media does not related to behavioral intention and actual visitation.

The perceived behavioral control in visiting cafes such as self-decision in terms of decision, control and stopping visiting cafes, self-efficacy in terms of right choice and right action, and facilitating condition in terms of access to my town in term of decision and access to my town in terms of high quality does not related to behavioral intention and actual visitation of cafes.

Therefore, the null hypothesis number two stated that the intention to visit on the actual behavior of visiting cafes is not related to attitude, influence of significant others and perceived behavioral control is not totally accepted.

Fishbein and Ajzen said that the most important determinant of a person's behavior is behavior intent. The individual's intention to perform a behavior is a combination of attitude performing the behavior and subjective norm. The individuals attitude toward the

behavior includes; behavioral beliefs, evaluations of behavioral outcome, subjective norm, normative beliefs, and the motivation to comply. If a person perceives that the outcome from performing a behavior is positive, she/ he will have a positive attitude forward performing that behavior. The opposite can be stated if the behavior is thought to be negative. If relevant others see performing the behavior as positive and the individual is motivated to meet the expectations of relevant others, then a positive subjective norms is expected. If relevant, others see the behavior as negative, and the individual wants to meet the expectations of these others, then the experience is likely to be a negative subjective norm for the individual.

Moreover, Icek Ajzen posits that beliefs about attitudes, control and norms influence behavior and are mediated by intentions. Intention fully mediates the effects of attitude and subjective norms on behavior, whereas perceived behavioral control has a double role in the TB. In situations where the individual has a very degree of control over the behavior, intention is sufficient predictor of the individual consumer. However, in situations where there are problems with control, perceived behavioral control should also contribute to the prediction of behavior, over and above its partially mediated effect thru intention, by serving as a proxy for actual behavioral control.

Conclusions

From the result of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Most of the visitors to cafes are females. Females are mostly decision-makers nowadays, as a result of the study.

Consumers' satisfaction in visiting cafés depends upon their experience of visiting cafes. How they become satisfied with consumption may be classified on their favorable feelings as good, pleasant, desirable, or relaxing and on their unfavorable feelings as bad, unpleasant, undesirable, or stressful. Enjoyment of visiting cafes could be important because it is a determinant to feel the good place of a café, and to understand the pleasure of the consumer, it is important to decide whether it is good or not for them to visit a cafe. Actual identity is either important or not important. It could be important for the town to patronize their cafe. However, it could be unimportant if the consumer does not want to visit cafes. It means that their decision depends upon their satisfaction with visiting the cafe.

The subjective norm is determined by the total set of readily accessible normative beliefs. Normative beliefs are beliefs about the normative expectations of others and motivation to comply with these expectations. It only implied that the influence of the respondent to visit a café was determined by influential and important people. The study found that influential people and important people strongly agree to encourage visiting cafes. It also implied that family and friends determine internal normative beliefs. The study found out that the consumers agree that their family and friends influenced them to visit cafes. Meanwhile, the external normative belief, such as colleagues and social media, pointed out that consumers agree to follow their colleague's advice or to be aware on social media to consider.

Like attitudes and subjective norms, perceptions of behavioral control are assumed to follow consistently from readily accessible beliefs, in this case beliefs about resources and obstacles that can facilitate or interfere with the performance of a given behavior. Consumers' agree that it is part of their personal decision on how they will or on what way they will visit cafes. Self-efficacy is the individual perception (that he/she will be able to perform a certain behavior. The study resulted as that consumers are agree on their right choice of visiting cafes and it is important on their right choice visiting cafes. Moreover, consumer are agree about their right action on visiting cafes and important for them. Nevertheless, behavior was considerably affected by individual intention and facilitating condition. It has been found out that consumer agree that visiting cafes in their town is their habit while whether or not consumer visit cafes from their town is an important part of their decision whether to visit cafes. Meanwhile, consumers are agree that they have convenient access to the market in terms of high quality cafes and to have a convenient access to the market high quality cafe is an important part of their decision to visit cafes.

Behavioral intention is an indication of an individual's readiness to perform a given behavior. However, it is assumed to be an immediate antecedent of behavior. The study found out that the consumers' expected visitation (socialize), (frequency) and (schedule) strongly agree with visiting cafes. This behavior indicated the preferred favorable intention of a consumer to when and how they visit cafes.

Although the demographic profiles are variables that have significant effects on the attitudes and other factors toward visiting cafes, as evident by various research, this study found otherwise and concluded that demographic profiles are not significant at all in influencing the factors on visiting in the context of this study.

The intention to consume based on the actual behavior of visiting cafes is not totally significantly related to attitude, influence of significant others, and perceived behavioral control.

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following are the recommendations:

Considerable that females should be aware of the right visitation of any cafes.

The consumer indicated that good ambience for a cafe is an important part of the consumer's quality perception and visit choice. Eating healthily and health concepts is subjective, and norms are considered to influence food intake.

This study was conducted to show that decision-making activities typically involve several friends who play a variety of roles in the

process. Furthermore, evidence is building that friends play a much greater role than family.

The consumers often report their expectations when answering behavioral intention questions. Clearly, there is a conceptual difference between behavioral goals and behavioral estimations for any consumer who has tried to achieve their certain goals.

To the business person, choose the right convenience market, which means that the market for convenience products is expanding. While they have traditionally appealed to consumers with little interest in other aspects of food quality, there now seems to be a rising demand for products with good taste, health, and process qualities that are at the same time convenient to buy, store, and use.

For demographic profiles, customers with different ages, genders, and educations may have different likes and dislikes. Therefore, marketing and promotion should focus on target market segments.

The researcher focused on the general scope of consumer behavior towards cafes. Additional probing questions about the relationship between intention and actual behavior in visitation of cafes.

To the future researcher may have them give a depth study on the study about the consumers behavior toward visitation.

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